

International Standards and Their Impact on Administrative Control

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Abstract : *In our article today, we talked about the definition of international standards related to administrative control, as well as the role of those standards in achieving administrative reform and improving better performance of institutions, with the aim of ensuring that those in charge of the control process possess competence, integrity and independence in planning, implementing and reporting the results of their work. However, these standards related to administrative control require the dissemination and support of a culture of applying international standards for issued supreme administrative control bodies.*

Keywords: International standards, administrative control.

I. INTRODUCTION

Administrative control is also one of the concepts related to openness and clarity, and it means that institutions have high transparency, that is, they know what is going on in them and revolves around them, in addition to clarifying their procedures and policies for their employees. Some researchers also considered it as a pivotal issue in the process of the development and prosperity of the institution, not to mention that it is not limited to supervision and accounting around the costs of the institution, but rather the control of all activities related to the institution internally and externally. And making sure you don't waste money. That is, the absence of administrative oversight makes it impossible for institutions to achieve any progress.

The researchers pointed out that administrative control helps prevent cases of corruption and fraud in all its forms, meaning that the transparency of institutional procedures and laws helps prevent deviations or breaches in them, and even helps in simplifying procedures, which leads to increased efficiency and effectiveness related to performance.

In their definition of administrative control, the researchers stated that it works to reduce the occurrence of any economic crises, and works to address the necessary and unnecessary issues before their escalation and expansion of their scope.

While others pointed out that there are several basic dimensions of administrative control agreed upon by many researchers, the most important of which was first: Credibility - and it is one of the main factors that affect the outputs of educational institutions, and it means reliability and confidence in the institution's activities and procedures, which generates satisfaction among those who deal with the institution compared to others. and thus increases the reliability of its performance. Second: Disclosure - The disclosure process means the institution's ability to show financial and human data and any data that takes place within the institution in a timely manner. Third: Clarity - Clarity is related to the institution's ability to create an appropriate atmosphere for the success of the institution's activities and operations.

II. HEADINGS

What are the international standards for management control?

The international standards for management control are divided into two parts (input standards and output standards. Let us first get acquainted with the input standards: they are standards designed to measure the efforts of workers to perform the tasks required by implementation or the specifications of the elements that go into the production process. Input standards depend on the measurement of Efforts that contribute to the performance of tasks, such as the extent to which employees adhere to a set of laws and procedures specified by the organization when

performing the tasks required of him, and that the production department in the organization determines specific specifications for the product so that it is acceptable to customers and easy to market.

Second, the output criteria: the criteria designed to measure performance results in terms of time, cost, quantity and quality. Examples of output standards include defining the quantity of production in quantity or number so that the worker is required to complete it daily, so it becomes a standard of performance.

But many researchers divided the criteria according to the method of evaluation, and they are divided into:

- Historical standards: These are standards that are based on comparing the standards of the current performance with the previous performance.
- Comparative criteria: It is based on comparing the current performance rates of the institution's performance with the performance rates of the competing or similar institution.
- Technical standards: These are based on calculating the time and activity required to perform work on studies and scientific means.

Regulatory standards by administrative type:

There are many different types of administrative control, and perhaps the most famous of them is external and internal control. Therefore, what is meant by "external oversight" is the presence of an independent body determined by the senior leadership in the government whose role is to monitor and evaluate the performance of its various sectors, through a detailed audit of the administrative and financial aspects, so that it monitors the deviations of the administrative work and the errors that taint it, and in another aspect it monitors any operations Excess, waste or misuse of public money. On both sides, the independent body that exercises the administrative and financial control process shall prepare its detailed reports on each observation, proposing solutions and remedies, and then making sure that the sectors implement these recommendations in order not to repeat mistakes and abuses.

This type of administrative control has recently begun to spread through countries establishing special bodies for administrative and financial control as well, in order to ensure the safety of operations and the achievement of their objectives and to ensure that financial budgets are spent in the correct aspects specified for them. As for what we mean by internal control, which is carried out by an internal administration that implements oversight operations and is directly subordinate to decision makers and those responsible for sectors at the top of the functional structure. It excludes any cadres, and submits its reports in detail to the higher authority with recommendations related to correction operations.

Other researchers indicated that administrative control differs in its types according to the size and nature of the work of organizations, which led to the need for the emergence of different types of administrative control, as a tool for measuring efficiency and effectiveness, in order to achieve integration, justice and equality. :

1. Administrative control according to the time frame for implementation:

- Interim administrative control: It means the administrative control over each stage of the plan after its implementation, and it takes place after dividing the plan into stages, and then the actual implementation results are measured after the completion of each stage, and compared with the standards set previously, since no administrative control is carried out on the actual implementation of a stage. Before making sure that the previous stage has actually taken place as planned.

- Administrative control after implementation: in this case, the administrative control activity begins when the plan is implemented, and its results are completed, by comparing the final actual results with the criteria established to identify deviations. A new plan, and this type of administrative control is usually used in routine work, where the error does not have a great weight.

2. Administrative oversight according to its subject:

- Positive administrative control: It aims to ensure that all procedures and actions are taken in accordance with the rules, regulations, and instructions in force within the organization to ensure the achievement of its objectives on the one hand, and the prediction of deviations and errors on the other hand.

- Negative administrative control: this administrative control works in the search for errors and deviations, and works to prevent their occurrence, with a focus on punishing the perpetrators of these errors and deviations, in other words, it works to trap errors and deviations.

Accordingly, the essential difference as seen in this study between the two previous types of oversight is that positive administrative control means good workflow, not catching errors as in negative administrative control, and based on that it can be said that the use of the differentiation criterion between the two previous types of administrative control is the level of civilized maturity, The environment of the organization, internally or externally.

3. Administrative control according to the quantity and quality of work:

- Administrative control over the quantity of work: This administrative control focuses on the quantity of productive work, that is, on the outputs, in order to know the regular changes in the size of those quantities of increase or decrease, and then search for the causes, and address the situation.

- Administrative control over the quality of work: It means a method by which service or production is accepted or rejected. Acceptance or rejection depends on the presence of objective criteria that measure the quality of work and its specifications.

- Prior administrative control: It is the preventive or preventive administrative control. In the sense that it prevents errors or abuses before they occur, as administrative control is carried out on financial transactions and actions, before making the decision on financial disposition or before issuing, concluding or implementing the disposition, in order to prevent violations, errors and extravagance.

- Concurrent (simultaneous) administrative control: it is the administrative control that accompanies and synchronizes with the implementation, so that it leads to the discovery of the error or deviation within a short period of its occurrence, and contributes to its correction, treatment, and its non-continuity or recurrence.

- Subsequent administrative control: it is the administrative control that takes place after the implementation of financial operations, and it is considered the main method through which the Audit Bureau exercises its control.

III. CONCLUSION

In conclusion, we must be fully aware that administrative control is not as understood by some and interpreted as catching the mistakes of employees and exercising ways of controlling them and killing the creativity and achievements of the members of the institution, but it is a means to achieve a kind of organization and effectiveness within the institution; Administrative control is the means by which the administrative authorities can know how the work is going inside the facility, in order to ensure the proper progress of the work to achieve the objectives and detect errors, omissions or deviations, and work to fix it and put in place the necessary preventive measures to eliminate its causes.

In addition, there are other branches of internal administrative control in any institution, which have aspects related to all elements of the work, such as control over financial and human resources, the progress of strategic plans and operational processes, and the implementation of projects, and its goal is to ensure that all things are going in the right way.

For the optimal application of administrative control processes, there are several methods that are applied as measurement tools that help in the process of control and making observations and then evaluation, the most famous of which is the adoption of administrative reports for each individual in the system, which is important to be developed based on performance standards linked to key objectives and that are measurable and verifiable, and these The process helps to show the level of performance of each employee individually, while giving room for direction, guidance and correction. In parallel, administrative supervision based on follow-up to the workflow is one of the important tools that are relied upon in the administrative control process, and here the role of middle management of managers, officials and supervisors is essential in following up on implementation and evaluation, making them help factors for the entity that undertakes the comprehensive administrative control process, with Note that continuous administrative supervision contributes significantly to the process of correcting any deviations, adjusting performance, enhancing the work of employees, empowering them and helping them to face difficulties and overcome obstacles.

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